

Gain yield of improved rice varieties at 7 farmers' fields in Wangdiphodrang-Punakha, Bhutan, 1986.

Item	Changoytang Punakha	Richa Punakha	Zomleytang Punakha	Khurutang Punakha	Misina Wangdiphodrang	Bajo Wangdiphodrang	Techuzamba Wangdiphodrang	Mean
<i>Soil characteristics</i>								
pH	6.8	5.6	6.9	5.9	5.7	6.4	5.9	
Organic C (%)	1.40	1.01	0.86	1.10	0.89	1.43	1.66	
Olsen P (ppm)	21	2.5	2.1	6.6	nil	16	13	
FYM (t/ha)	12	14	6	20	10	12	(applied to preceding wheat)	
<i>Grain yield (t/ha)</i>								
IR36	5.6	6.0	4.5	5.1	3.5	3.4	7.0	5.0
IR64	5.5	6.7	4.5	5.0	3.8	3.6	7.6	5.2
Milyang 49	4.2	5.7	4.2	4.1	3.1	3.0	6.2	4.4
IR25670-15-2-3	3.5	5.2	3.8	3.7	3.2	3.2	5.7	4.1
Local check	4.5	6.3	4.0	3.3	3.4	3.1	6.8	4.5
Site mean	4.6	6.0	4.2	4.2	3.4	3.2	3.3	
CV (%)	7.0	6.2	3.9	8.9	8.6	5.6	4.2	
LSD (0.05)	0.6	0.7	0.3	0.7	0.6	0.3	0.5	

Olsen available P ranged from 2.1 to 21 ppm (see table). Levels of available K and other plant nutrients were generally adequate. The land was manured and prepared by cooperator farmers. Estimates of farmyard manure (FYM) applied at each site are shown in the table.

Seedlings of test varieties IR36, IR64, Milyang 49, IR25670-15-2-3, and K39-96-1-1-1-2, and the local check varieties were raised in farmers' dry bed nurseries and (except the check varieties) in standby nurseries at CARD in Apr and early May. In June, seedlings of each variety from farmers' nurseries (or from CARD) were transplanted in line at a spacing of 20 × 20 cm in 2 × 5 m plots at each site. The plots were arranged in a randomized complete block with three replications per site. Weedings were by rotary weeder and by hand once or twice between 22 and 43 d after transplanting, depending on weed pressure. Irrigations were managed by cooperator farmers. K39-96-1-1-1-2 matured considerably earlier than the other varieties, but no representative yields were obtained because it was seriously damaged by rats at most sites. There were no other significant pests or diseases. Plot yields of the remaining varieties were computed at 14% moisture content.

IR36 and IR64 were consistently good, and Milyang 49 and IR25670-15-2-3 consistently poor across sites. Individual check variety yields fluctuated substantially across sites,

resulting in a significant (P=0.05) site × variety interaction in a combined analysis of variance of all sites. Using the site × variety mean square for trend examination across sites showed IR36 and IR64 to be highly significantly superior (P=0.01) to Milyang 49 and IR25670-15-2-3. The latter two did not significantly differ from the check varieties at all sites: IR64 yield was consistently higher than that of the check varieties (significant at five sites) and tended to be higher than that of

IR36, although this difference was not significant in the combined site analysis of variance. IR64 is taller than IR36, has stiffer straw and, because of its intermediate amylose grain, is similar in eating quality, to local varieties. Like IR36, however, it is susceptible to drought stress in local dry bed nurseries and to cold stress if planted toward the end of the local planting season.

IR64 showed wide adaptability and may be more suitable than IR36 for increasing rice output in the valley. □

IR21820-154-3-2-2-3, a new, medium-duration rice variety released in Tamil Nadu as ADT38

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IR21820-154-3-2-2-3, isolated from the cross IR1529-680-3-2/IR4432-52-6-4// IR7963-30-2 and locally designated AD85004, was identified as the most promising high-yielding entry under thaladi (Oct-Jan) situations in the Cauvery Delta zone. This cultivar was evaluated at TNRRI for 4 yr. Based on its consistent performance, it was released in May 1987 as ADT38 for general cultivation in Tamil Nadu in samba and thaladi seasons, as an alternate to IR20 and Co 43.

The mean grain yield over 4 yr in research station trials (5.9 t/ha) showed

Table 1. Performance of ADT38 in research station and adaptive research trials. Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India, 1983-86.

Year	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	ADT38	Co 43	IR20
<i>Research station trials</i>			
1983	7.2	5.7	4.2
1984	5.3	4.4	4.3
1985	6.0	5.1	4.9
1986	5.0	4.2	3.5
Mean	5.9	4.9	4.3
<i>Adaptive research trials^a</i>			
1986	6.2	5.2	5.5

^a37 locations.

20 and 37% increases over Co 43 and IR20 (Table 1). In adaptive research trials in 37 farmers' fields, mean grain yield (6.2 t/ha) showed 19 and 13% increases over Co 43 and IR20. Its overall performance in the trials of All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project and the International Rice

Testing Program was also good.

ADT38 is a dwarf (80-85 cm), nonlodging, and heavy-tillering rice with a duration of 130-135 d. The grain is medium slender, fine, and white. Milling recovery is 68%, and cooking quality is good.

ADT38 was screened under artificial conditions for the important pests and diseases of the area (Table 2). It possesses resistance to blast (BI), brown spot (BS), green leafhopper (GLH), and

Table 2. Reaction of ADT38 and IR20 to insect pests and diseases under controlled screening.

Variety	Score ^a								
	BI	BB	RTV	BS	BPH	WBPH	GLH	LF	GM
ADT38	0	7	5	2	5	1	3	5	5
IR20	3	5	9	2	7	9	9	9	9

^aBy Standard evaluation system for rice.

whitebacked planthopper (WBPH). It is also moderately resistant to tungro (RTV), brown planthopper (BPH), leaffolder (LF), and gall midge (GM). □

Comparison of IR36 and Local varieties of rice in farmers' fields in Bhutan

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In the Wangdiphodrang-Punakha valley, interest in modern fertilizer-responsive, high-yielding rice varieties is growing. Production of acceptable amounts of straw for animal fodder in winter is also important. We studied the performance of IR36 at 13 sites in the valley at altitudes between 1,200 and 1,450 m. Data were analyzed as a randomized complete block design, with sites as blocks and variety-management combinations as treatments.

Soils were sandy to clay loam, pH 4.5-6.2, with 1% organic C or less, and low (<10 ppm) to moderate (15-20 ppm) Olsen available P. Soil fertility is maintained by annual additions of an average 7 t farmyard manure (FYM)/ ha. At most study sites, farmers applied an estimated 9-14 t FYM/ha, but some sites received none.

In late May and in June, farmers transplanted 37- to 60-d-old IR36 seedlings adjacent to the local variety in terraced fields so that, at each site, about one-half to two-thirds of a typical field was planted to IR36 and the rest to the local variety. The crops were managed following local practices. A portion of the IR36 plot (separated from the rest of the IR36 by a bund) had improved

Mean yields of IR36 and local rice varieties in 13 farmers' fields.^a Wangdiphodrang-Punakha valley, Bhutan, 1986.

Site	Local management				Improved management ^b	
	Local variety		IR36		IR36	
	Grain ^c (t/ha)	Straw ^d (t/ha)	Grain ^c (t/ha)	Straw ^d (t/ha)	Grain ^c (t/ha)	Straw ^d (t/ha)
1 ^e	5.16	17.13	4.46	na	4.14	na
2	4.52	15.60	4.99	5.27	5.48	5.80
3 ^f	3.11	na	3.36	na	4.72	na
4	4.29	12.90	4.43	na	5.76	na
5	4.88	15.40	6.66	11.06	7.86	10.00
6 ^{eg}	3.79	11.80	3.62	na	4.43	na
7	4.28	na	5.87	na	5.92	na
8	2.93	na	4.59	6.93	5.30	9.80
9	4.21	14.20	5.39	na	7.05	na
10 ^f	3.92	10.80	4.22	5.80	4.16	6.40
11 ^f	3.77	12.20	4.72	na	3.91	na
12	4.18	12.14	4.91	6.66	6.63	9.46
13	5.69	25.40	7.69	17.07	8.70	19.40
Mean	4.21	14.76	4.96	8.79	5.69	10.14
Grain increase (%) over local	0	-	17.7	-	34.7	-
MBCR ^h	0	-	5.3	-	6.8	-
LSD (0.05) grain over all sites				0.56		
CV (%) grain over all sites				14		

^a na = not available. ^b 35 kg N/ha plus weeding at 30-40 DT. ^c At 14% moisture content. ^d Fresh weight at harvest. ^e IR36 affected by severe weed competition. ^f IR36 adversely affected by water stress at tillering or flowering. ^g Low soil fertility. ^h Based on rice seed cost of \$30/ha, urea plus application cost of \$46/ha, rough rice price of \$0.21/kg.

management: urea topdressing and weeding at panicle initiation (30-40 d after transplanting [DT]). Grain yields were estimated from replicated 5-m² crop cuts from the local variety and IR36 under local and improved management at each site. Where possible, straw yield at harvest was also obtained.

IR36 was susceptible to drought at the nursery stage, and at two sites where water shortage was prolonged, farmers' IR36 seedlings had to be replaced with

seedlings from CARD. Pests and diseases were insignificant during the study. IR36 crop duration (161-177 d, mean 170) allowed harvest 4 to 30 d (mean 9 d) earlier than most of the local varieties.

IR36 grain yield was 18% higher (P=0.05) than that of the local varieties averaged over sites (see table). With improved management, IR36 yielded 35% more grain (P=0.05) than local varieties. At individual sites, IR36 grain yield was 3.6-7.7 t/ha for farmers'